

TYPES OF FINE ARTS SUBJECTS TAUGHT IN SCHOOLS OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

Adhamova Oltinoy Rafiqjon qizi

Student of the direction "Fine Arts and engineering graphics" of the
Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

Solijonova Muhtasarxon Jahongir qizi

Student of the direction "Fine Arts and engineering graphics" of the
Andijan State Pedagogical

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Annotation: This article reflects on the types of Fine Arts exercises that are carried out in schools of general secondary education, the purpose tasks of the subject of study, the importance of practical exercises in improving the creative abilities of students, and gives several recommendations.

Key words: School, Fine Arts, lesson, younger generation, abilities, Color Image, creativity, Image, Graphics.

Today, the education of young people in every possible way, competently and immature, is one of the most important goals of our society. The fact that our state supports young people and opens the door to tremendous opportunities for them is also the most gratifying situation. Because every younger generation is the foundation and founder of tomorrow. In addition to the fact that our young people are now offered a wide range of opportunities, all the conditions are sufficient for their quality education. Since Uzbekistan follows the path of building a democratic legal state, it is the first and most important task of our state to comprehensively improve free Shaha and create all conditions in this regard. Therefore, the field of education is rising to the level of Public Policy. Our first president was I.A. Karimov noted in his work "high spirituality is an invincible force", "the future of our Motherland, the tomorrow of our people, the place of our country in the world community, the attention of prestige is primarily a link to the fact that our children grow up and grow up and mature into what kind of person they come to life. The role of our educational institutions, in particular our secondary schools, where children are first savored, is incomparable in how they grow up as human beings. The process of bringing education and upbringing, which is carried out today in secondary schools, has become much more developed and progressive than in previous years. Today, there are several tasks of our schools, one of which consists in directing young people to various professions and professions, developing aesthetic education in them and forming thinking, in general, developing young students in every possible way and educating them as a harmonious generation. In the formation of the aesthetic worldview of students, in the exaltation of artistic thinking, in the teaching of logical and creative thinking, in the development of imagination and memory, creativity and fantasy, the tasks that are set before the Fine Arts in secondary schools are solved. Because the visual arts quickly reach the human mind, enrich the spiritual world and evoke noble feelings in children and in the human soul. Increases interest in reading a person, and especially young people. In general, fine art is of great importance in educating young people competently.

In fine arts classes, students effectively influence mental, moral, quasi-educational training. At the same time, it serves to develop several aspects, such as vision, perception, observation, imagination, etc. Fine arts classes shape national pride and national perspective in children,

educate students in the spirit of patriotism, serve as a great force in maturing feelings such as friendship and mutual respect. In the lessons of "Fine Arts", the first interest of students in art Awakens. During classes, students will also learn about works of art and the work and lifestyle of great artists. During the fine arts classes, they acquire a great deal of knowledge in the genres of Arts, Sculpture, graphics, painting, Applied Arts and history, animal, domestic, landscape and still life. When it comes to the educational subject of visual art, it is impossible not to dwell on its functions either. It should be remembered that the Fine Arts at school are inextricably linked with all valuable subjects. They have a significant effect on the assimilation of materials in the expression. It is of particular importance in a number of classes, such as reading, geography, natural science, history. Zero educational processes have been subjected to the influence of interdependent, spiritual, economic psychological, technological distribution. This process is a key factor in the maturation of healthy-minded individuals, free from a wide talented worldview of children. In school fine arts classes, students study processes ranging from imaging, painting, graphics, design to modeling according to NARS himself. Especially in "graphics", one of the most popular types of visual art, children learn to work in a pencil or dream. They will have a lot of information about the aesthetics of stalls with books, newspapers, magazines, items and posters, graphic records. People watch works of Fine Art and express their attitude to the events, circumstances, beauties reflected in them. Representing people, manifestations of nature, phenomena, objects on flat surfaces or by various means-is called visual art. When it comes to the tasks of Fine Arts classes at school, they can be conditionally divided into two parts:

1. Specific, special tasks of Fine Arts classes are considered: to teach to see, perceive, understand and appreciate beauties in existence and art; to cultivate aesthetic and artistic taste; to expand the range of children's artistic thought; to develop artistic creative abilities and fantasy; to introduce the theoretical foundations of Fine Arts (light, color science, perspective, composition); to work painting, sculpt, build art - make elements; observation, memory of vision, the ability to Champ, the development of spatial and figurative representations, abstract and logical thinking; teaching to be able to read visual, practical architectural works of art with understanding; to arouse interest in art, to teach it to appreciate, to love.

2. Additional tasks of Fine Arts classes, they are: to promote the knowledge of being, life; the implementation of the ideology of national pride and national independence; moral (patriotic, International) in children; the implementation of labor, physical education; the orientation of children to various professions and professions.

The visual arts are divided into 3 types according to the means of expression:

1. Color Image. 2. Sculpture. 3. Graphics.

In the direction of the "Color Image", which is most attractive in visual art, students learn to artistically depict life phenomena, objects, on paper or on a flat surface using paints. Color is said to be an image, performed using different colors and materials on a flat surface. For this species, paints are mainly used –oil paint, watercolor, gouache, tempera, as well as colored pencils, pastel, sanguinas. Painting works are processed on flat surfaces such as paper, fabric, cardboard, wall, mirror, wood. The basis of the painting is the painting. In any painting work, first of all, its painting is produced. Composition, light and shade, color occupy the main place in it.

Sculpture is the expression of various images, events in volume. In sculpture, materials such as stone, metal, plaster, wood, wax are widely used. A bust is called when only the head part and shoulder of a person are worked. A sculpture is called If a person is worked with a bow-stick.

"Graphic - "is a Latin word meaning" I write"," I draw", and is a form of Fine Art. One of the peculiarities of a graph is that it is not large in size and the number of paints is limited (mainly a black - and-white image). That is why only a line or a dark color image is involved in graphic works. Some graphic works are made in large sizes and in many copies and perform large educational tasks. Such graphic works are called posters.

There are the following types of Color Image:

1. Machine painting.
2. Monumental (majestic) painting.
3. Miniature painting.
4. Decorative painting.
5. Theater-decorative painting.

Visual arts at the school is considered the main subject of study aimed at the implementation of aesthetic education, which is carried out in the following areas:

- teaching students to perceive the beauties of nature, art and life:
- the ability to educate the aesthetic taste of students, to assess beauty, to teach good beauty to be able to distinguish it from a chronic event and things;
- to be able to show oneself in the pictorial-creative activity of a person, to support his actions and to cultivate the skills to bring beauty to life:
- expanding the artistic thought circle of children, etc.

One of the most important tasks of Fine Arts classes is to teach the reading of works of fine, applied and Architectural Arts. Works of Fine Arts reflect a certain content, such as a fairy tale, a story, a saga, a novel. However, it cannot be read as if it were a book. Fine art works have their own language. Only those who know them can read them. In particular, artists reveal the content of the work using expressive means such as lines, colors, measures, composition, proportion, symmetry form. In this regard, it should be noted that works of art, especially works of the historical, living genre, contain full-fledged and comprehensive information about certain peoples and countries. Only those individuals who can read these can deeply perceive the ideas put forward in the works, the content described. They can also determine the artistic value of a work and give it an appropriate assessment. Alternatively, they produce satisfaction and pleasure from such qualities as beauty in works, ascendancy, chivalry. The educational subject of Fine Arts is relevant not only in the aesthetic education of young people, but also occupies a significant place in moral education. Especially fine arts classes have great power in the formation of the ideology of national pride and national independence in young people, in patriotic and international education, in the organization of ideas of friendship and mutual assistance. Looking at the school's fine arts program, we will see in it that the Great past of our Motherland, the struggle of our compatriots for independence, the breathtaking nature of Uzbekistan, overflowing with works of Fine Arts expressing the ideas of friendship of peoples. For example, there are works of fine art that represent the lives and images of our great compatriots, such as Amir Temur, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Spitamen, Mukhanna, the beautiful landscapes of colorful, Uzbekistan, the peaceful work of the Uzbek people with other nationalities living in our Republic. In the

process of their study, children get acquainted with the laws and rules of art, work Pictures in the above-mentioned content, work on a picture of still lifes made of sweet-sugar and colorful fruits, flowers of Uzbekistan, as a result of which such qualities as love for the motherland and their people, national pride are formed. The peculiarity of Visual Arts in elementary grades, first of all, the content of education is determined by the age characteristics and psychology, interest, ability and competence of children of a small school age. In schools of general secondary education, the content of education is determined based on the goals and objectives of the educational subject of Fine Arts and based on the state standards of Education. The Fine Arts Program defines the following five types:

1. Perception of being (primary classes).
2. Artistic construction-making (primary education).
3. Fundamentals of art studies (secondary education).
4. Description by nature (secondary education).
5. Compositional activity (secondary education).

Perception of being plays an important role in the growth of students ' aesthetic perception, taste, concepts of this field, imagination and memories. The classes of perception of being are usually held before the performance of thematic compositions, in which it is assumed to be able to see the elegance and beauty of nature and surroundings, to use the obtained as a result of perception in practical artistic-creative activities. Also, in the process of traveling to nature, raw drawings of certain objects and phenomena are also processed using pencils, paints and other artistic materials, if necessary. In such classes, children observe plants, animals, birds, fish outside the classroom and Classroom, get an idea of the manifestations of nature in different seasons, their (sad, thoughtful, etc.). Observing being in beginner classes and conversations about them will help students get to know some phenomena in life more broadly. It also allows you to grow such important qualities as analyzing and generalizing in a certain amount, such as the shape, structure, color of things. In the process of observing nature and being, children are taught to love, preserve it. On trips to nature, the fact that certain aspects of them change depending on the seasons is explained to children. Also in this, the phasic imagination of children is grown, and the emphasis is placed on planning, linear and aerial perspective. The consciousness of children is conveyed that the observation of being is directly related to pictorial creative activity, it is impossible to perform qualitative pictorial work without knowing the being. Now that schools have few hours of fine arts classes compared to other subjects, student youth's interest in the subject remains thirsty. With the increase in the hours of classes in fine arts in schools, the spiritual world of students is rich, the worldview is wide, creative skills are strong, aesthetic education is more formed. The creative processes in the continuation of the lessons of Fine Arts give joy and spirit to the student youth, in which creative abilities are further formed. tasks and assignments in the continuation of closely help the reader to more accurately perceive being, to form the ability to think in young people. Alternatively, it teaches meticulous observation of the structure, shape, color, size and spatial States of things and phenomena, forming a number of distinctive features, such as Vision, observability. The peculiarity of this observability is that in this case, students perceive the state of things and phenomena more easily than other people and get a deeper picture. This, in turn, affects the memory of information about well-preserved things. We are also faced with the fact that in several schools of our country, the subjects of Fine Arts are not passed on by their specialists in science. What does this science teach students as a

result ?, how are paints used?, what rules to follow when painting? they do not fully understand the few information they say, and this, in turn, leads to the fact that the lesson is ineffective. It is known that in the process of educational education, the education of primary classes is a separate stage, during which the most intensive period of development and growth of the child's personality occurs. Therefore, the transition of a visual arts specialist to a primary student also leads to the development of children in relation to this subject, as well as an increase in these interests. The peculiarity of Visual Arts in elementary grades, first of all, the content of education is determined by the age characteristics and psychology of children of a small school age, their warmth, talent, ability and especially ability. When students start painting, they try to make their paintings creative, irreversible. On the contrary, the requirements for the process of teaching the Fine Arts encourage students to create unique works ,to work more on themselves.

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